

Influence of N, Ar and Si ion implantation on the passive layer and corrosion behaviour of AISI 304 and 430 stainless steels

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Abstract

Specimens of AISI 304 and AISI 430 stainless steels (SS) were implanted with nitrogen, argon and silicon up to an ion dose of 1×10^{15} ion/cm² at an accelerating potential of 150 keV. AISI 304 and 430 SS specimens were analysed as-received and after ion implantation using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) in conjunction with Ar⁺-ion sputtering. Surface chromium enrichment was observed with the argon ion-implanted specimens compared with the non-implanted specimens, enhancing their corrosion resistance. Nitrogen implantation does not seem to have a significant effect on the structure and composition of the passive layer. Finally, silicon-implanted SSs show a very different passive layer, in which SiO₂ is the main component of the outer surface.

Keywords: Ion implantation; Stainless steel; Corrosion resistance; X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

1. Introduction

Stainless steels (SS) are materials of great interest in technological applications. The stability of the surface oxide (i.e. passive film) formed on a SS depends mainly on the passivation time, temperature, alloy composition and working environment. The solid state properties of the passive film have been widely studied using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) and X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) techniques [1– 4]. These studies have shown that the passive film formed on a SS exposed to aqueous solutions are Cr-enriched close to the alloy, with hydroxide and water-containing compounds concentrated in the outermost region of the film and chromium oxide enrichment at the metal-film interface.

The ion implantation technique as a surface modification method presents some advantages over other techniques: (i) high temperatures are not needed; (ii) the bulk material remains unaffected after the implantation process; and (iii) the surface to be modified can be tailored by controlling the accelerating potential and the implantation dose [5].

The changes introduced on the SS surface by ion implantation can be evaluated by testing the outer layer's chemical composition, which may influence the corrosion behaviour of the alloy. In recent studies, AES and XAS were used to determine the presence of implanted species on the steel surface [6,7].

The aim of this paper is to investigate by the XPS technique the influence of nitrogen, silicon and argon ion implantation on the chemical composition and structure of the surface of the AISI 304 and AISI 430 alloys and on the Cr/Fe ratio, which affects their corrosion properties. The corrosion behaviour of the tested materials is also studied. The results are compared with argon sputtering measurements.

2. Experimental

AISI 304 (Cr: 18.30 wt.%, Ni: 8.19) austenitic SS and AISI 430 (Cr: 16.50 wt.%, Ni: 0.21, C: 0.064) ferritic SS were the materials tested. The AISI 304 and AISI 430 specimens were implanted using an accelerating potential of 80 keV up to an ion dose of 1×10^{15} ions/cm² for N, Si and Ar. Both AISI 304 and AISI 430 SSs were studied as-received and after Si, N and Ar ion implantation. The native oxide layer of the SS was not removed prior to the implantation process.

The ions (N, Si and Ar) were obtained from a Penning ion source with a maximum acceleration voltage of 300 kV. The ion beam current was 400 nA and the implantation lasted for 1 h 53 min, ensuring a low testing temperature (below 200 °C). A diffusion pump generated a vacuum of 10^{-7} Torr in the acceleration cabinet. The cabinet was equipped with a rotating circular specimen holder of 9-cm diameter.

Silicon was chosen because its addition enhances the localised corrosion resistance of SSs by increasing the stability of the passive layer [8–12]. Nitrogen implantation has met with varying degrees of success, ranging from beneficial to detrimental effects [13], depending on the implantation energy, the temperature reached during the process and the test solution used [10]. The response of the implanted material is dependent upon its solubility limit. If the implanted N remains in solid solution it may generate “expanded austenite” [14], increasing the localised corrosion resistance. However, if the solubility limit is exceeded, the precipitation of chromium and iron nitrides takes place and a decrease in the corrosion resistance is observed [15–18]. In the present work, no evidence of nitride precipitation was observed in either the AISI 304 or AISI 430 SSs. Finally, the implantation of argon leads to physical modifications on the SS by breaking its crystalline structure and changing the surface morphology [19]. Argon implantation was performed in order to test whether the modification observed with ion implantation are predominantly due to the chemical effect of the implanted element or to the physical modifications induced by ion implantation. Noble gases like neon have not proven to be beneficial for enhancing corrosion resistance, because of the high dislocation density induced in the crystalline structure [20,21]. The choice of ion and the amount of energy employed in the implantation process were the controlling factors of the modifications induced in the SSs [22]. In metallurgical experiments an implantation energy of 80 keV is considered to be an intermediate value. High values originate a deep distribution and reduce the effect of the ion implantation process, while low energies can produce an ion distribution fairly close to the surface and originate highly damaged regions. In the case of N implantation the amount of energy employed is particularly important. For instance, in tribology experiments the energies commonly used range between 10 and 40 keV, yielding different degrees of success in terms of corrosion resistance [23,24]. The reason for this behaviour is that the ion distribution closer to the surface increases the nitrogen concentration, generating a supersaturation of the structure and favouring nitride precipitation, which is detrimental for the material’s corrosion resistance properties. Furthermore, low energy implantation induces preferential sputtering along the grainboundaries and in certain crystallographic directions [25].

Fig. 1 shows implantation profiles performed using the TRIM 2003 computational code [26], obtaining the range (R), projected range (PR) and range deviation (DPR) parameters. Comparison of the implanted N, Si and Ar profiles on AISI 304 SS shows that the lighter the ion, the higher the PR achieved; in other words, nitrogen obtained the deepest penetration with the widest distribution, remaining in an inner region of the bulk. In contrast, argon obtained a shallower distribution due to the larger ion size, achieving the lowest PR value, and silicon implantation obtained intermediate values between nitrogen and argon. The simulation on the AISI 430 SS yielded similar results, although its less compact structure allowed a deeper penetration of the implanted ions (between 2 and 6 nm deeper).

Polarisation resistance (R_p) (corrosion potential (E_{corr}) \pm 20 mV) and Tafel polarisation measurements (β_a and β_c parameters) (E_{corr} \pm 250 mV) were performed in a 0.5 M sodium chloride (NaCl) test solution. A three-electrode configuration method was utilised, with a Ag/AgCl reference electrode, a graphite bar as counter electrode and the N-, Ar- or Si-implanted specimen as working electrode, with a surface area of 2.1 cm². A PAR EG&G, model 283, potentiostat was used. For R_p and Tafel experiments a scan rate of 0.166 mV/s was used.

XPS experiments were conducted using a VG Microtech model MT 500 electron spectrometer with an Mg $K\alpha_{1,2}$ anode X-ray source ($h\nu = 1253.6$ eV), with a primary beam energy of 15 kV and an electron current of 20 mA. The pressure in the

analysis cabinet was maintained at 1×10^{-9} Torr throughout the measurements. The regions of interest were Fe $2p_{3/2}$, Cr $2p_{3/2}$, O $1s$, C $1s$, Si $2p$, N $1s$, Ar $2p$ and Ni $2p_{3/2}$. The binding energy (BE) scale of the spectrophotometer was periodically calibrated using Ag $3d_{5/2}$ (368.3 eV, BE) and Au $4f_{7/2}$ (84.0 eV, BE) substrates. The full width at half-maximum (FWHM) obtained for the Ag $3d_{5/2}$ line is 0.9 eV. High-resolution spectra were recorded using 20 eV pass energy. A Shirley background subtraction was made to obtain the XPS signal intensity. The peaks were fitted using a Gaussian/Lorentzian product function.

The specimens were analysed as-received and after 1, 6 and 21 min of Ar^+ -ion sputtering at an etching rate $\approx 5 \text{ \AA}/\text{min}$. Ar^+ -ion sputtering was carried out with a primary beam energy of 5 kV and an ion density of $1 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, recording the corresponding spectrum for each sputtering cycle. The specimen storage time between ion implantation and characterisation was 4 weeks.

Fig. 1. TRIM implantation profiles for N, Si and Ar on AISI 304 SS using 10000 ions.

3. Results and discussion

Figs. 2 and 3 show high resolution O $1s$ spectra for AISI 304 and AISI 430 SS specimens as-received and after argon, nitrogen and silicon ion implantation. All the spectra show similar features, except for the Si-implanted SS. Oxygen spectra can be deconvoluted in three components: the main peak located at 531.7 eV BE corresponding to Fe and/or Cr hydroxides; a smaller peak located at 529.8 eV BE corresponding to Fe and Cr oxides; and a third peak at 533.0 eV BE corresponding to adsorbed water. In Si-implanted specimens, the main component of the O $1s$ spectra is located at 532.2 eV BE and may be attributed to SiO_2 [27], and a second peak is located at 533.2 eV BE corresponding to adsorbed water. No evidence of metallic oxides or hydroxides is found in these spectra (see Figs. 2 and 3).

Fig. 2. Oxygen 1s XPS spectra for as-received and Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI 304 SS specimens.

Figs. 4 and 5 show high resolution Fe 2p_{3/2} spectra for AISI 304 and AISI 430 SS specimens. As in Figs. 2 and 3, the spectra for all the specimens with the exception of the Si-implanted specimens show similar deconvolution, corresponding to Fe³⁺ oxides (at 710.6 eV BE) and Fe²⁺ oxides (at 709.2 eV BE). On the other hand the Si-implanted specimens show no Fe signal, indicating that Fe compounds are not present on the outer surface of the passive layer.

Fig. 3. Oxygen 1s XPS spectra for as-received and Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI 430 SS specimens.

Fig. 4. Iron $2p_{3/2}$ XPS spectra for as-received and Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI 304 SS specimens.

Figs. 6 and 7 show high resolution Cr $2p_{3/2}$ spectra for AISI 304 and AISI 430 SS specimens. Similar features to Fe $2p_{3/2}$ (Figs. 4 and 5) can be observed. The chromium signal is not present in the Si-implanted specimens of either stainless steel. In the other specimens, chromium is present as Cr^{3+} oxide (at 576.2 eV BE) and Cr^{3+} hydroxide (at 577.4 eV BE). Neither metallic chromium (at 574.1 eV BE) nor hexavalent compound (at 580.1 eV BE) signals are present in the XPS spectra.

Fig. 8 shows high resolution XPS spectra for implanted elements: Ar 2p for argon-implanted AISI 304 and AISI 430 SS specimens; N 1s for nitrogen-implanted AISI 304 and AISI 430 SS specimens; and Si 2p for silicon-implanted AISI 304 and AISI 430 SS specimens. These spectra show that implanted elements are present in the passive layer of the stainless steels. The position of the Si 2p peak, at 102.2 eV BE, corresponds to SiO_2 [27], in agreement with the O 1s deconvolution for these specimens (Figs. 2 and 3). These results indicate that the outer surface of the passivating layer of Si-implanted SS has a significant amount of SiO_2 , without metallic oxides or hydroxides. The position of the N 1s peak, at 400.0 eV BE, indicates that nitrogen is not forming Fe or Cr nitrides, which are located at lower binding energies (397.2 – 397.3 eV BE) [28,29].

Fig. 5. Iron $2p_{3/2}$ XPS spectra for as-received and Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI 430 SS specimens.

Fig. 6. Chromium $2p_{3/2}$ XPS spectra for as-received and Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI 304 SS specimens.

Previous studies performed by the authors [30], using glancing angle XPS measurements without argon sputtering, revealed that the implanted argon remained inside the structure of both AISI 304 and AISI 430 SSs.

Figs. 9 and 10 include depth profile compositions for AISI 304 and AISI 430 SS specimens, obtained using Ar^+ -ion sputtering up to 21 min for as-received specimens and up to 6 min for implanted specimens. The values in Figs. 9 and 10 were obtained from the intensities of the corresponding XPS spectra using sensitivity factors [31]. C, mainly arising from the contamination layer, was excluded from the calculations, for up to 6 min of sputtering O is the main component, indicating that the passive layer is composed of Fe and Cr oxides and hydroxides. After 21 min of sputtering the O signal has decreased and the Fe and Cr signals have increased to levels close to the content in the bulk specimen. The Ni signal appears for AISI 304 SS after sputtering, indicating the presence of the metal phase. The main feature of the Ar- and N-implanted specimens of both steels is the appearance of small amounts of the implanted elements. With both AISI 304 and AISI 430 SS, the amount of N is higher in the outermost layer and decreases with the sputtering time, while Ar is found deeper in the passive layer and increases with sputtering time. On the other hand, Si-implanted specimens show a different pattern, with a thick carbon layer that does not disappear after 6 min of Ar^+ -ion sputtering and a very important amount of oxygen and silicon. This suggests that in Si-implanted steels there is a thick layer of C, Si and O compounds over the metallic oxides and/or hydroxides.

Fig. 7. Chromium $2p_{3/2}$ XPS spectra for as-received and Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI 430 SS specimens.

Fig. 11 shows the Cr/Fe ratio in the passive layer of all the specimens, on the original surface and after 1 and 6 min of Ar^+ -ion sputtering. This parameter is very important from the corrosion resistance viewpoint, because a higher Cr/Fe ratio value is related with greater corrosion resistance. As can be observed, only Ar-implanted specimens present a significant increase in the Cr/Fe ratio, compared with the as-received SS specimens, suggesting improved corrosion resistance. In Si-implanted SSs the Cr/Fe ratio in specimens without sputtering cannot be calculated, since neither Cr nor Fe can be found in the passive layer. Nevertheless, this parameter may be insignificant from the corrosion resistance viewpoint for Si-implanted SSs, as the corrosion resistance of these specimens may be increased by the SiO_2 present in the outermost layer.

It should be noted that the Cr/Ni ratio for the AISI 304 SS has not been included in this discussion because the Ni signal was not detected in the passive layer.

Fig. 12 shows polarisation resistance (R_p) measurements for AISI 304 SS with the implanted elements. An important increase in the R_p value, and therefore an increase in the protective properties of the AISI 304 SS, can be observed after ion implantation. The biggest increase in R_p was obtained with argon implantation, followed by nitrogen and finally silicon, in which a 5-fold increase in the R_p value was found. These results are consistent with the XPS studies, as the Ar-implanted specimen is the only one that showed a significant increase in the Cr/Fe ratio. On the other hand, the Si-implanted specimen presented a SiO_2 layer in the outermost region that also affords additional protection to the AISI 304 SS. Finally, even though the N-implanted specimen did not show a significant increase in the Cr/Fe ratio, this was sufficient to promote an increase in the corrosion protection to the AISI 304 SS.

Fig. 8. Argon 2p, nitrogen 1s and silicon 2p XPS spectra for Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI 304 and 430 SS specimens

Fig. 9. Depth profiles for as-received and Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI304 SS specimens.

Fig. 10. Depth profiles for as-received and Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI430 SS specimens.

Fig. 11. Cr/Fe ratios derived from the corresponding XPS spectra of as-received and Ar-, N- and Si-implanted AISI 304 and 430 SS specimens.

Fig. 12. R_p for non-implanted and N-, Ar- and Si-implanted AISI 304 SS specimens.

Fig. 13 shows R_p measurements for AISI 430 SS with the implanted elements. In this case a different behaviour from Fig. 12 was obtained, and though all the implantation tests raised the R_p value, the Ar-implanted specimen showed a similar R_p value to the untreated AISI 430 SS specimen. The biggest increase in the R_p value was obtained with Si implantation. The Si-rich layer in the outermost region provides great protection to the AISI 430 SS. However, the Cr/Fe ratio for the Ar-implanted specimen was not as favourable as in the AISI 304 SS and, as a consequence, a slight variation of the R_p values was obtained. In the N-implanted specimen, where a decrease in the Cr/Fe ratio was observed, an increase in the protective properties was obtained, reaching intermediate values between Si and Ar. The reason for this behaviour may be that ion implantation promotes important physical and chemical modifications on the surface, whose combination results in unique surface properties. In the case of argon implantation on AISI 430 SS, the damage induced with ion implantation seems to be more important than with nitrogen implantation and, therefore, a smaller increase in R_p was registered.

Fig. 13. R_p for non-implanted and N-, Ar- and Si-implanted AISI 430 SS specimens.

In order to obtain more information on the corrosion resistance of ion-implanted AISI 304 SS, Tafel experiments were performed. Fig. 14 shows the evolution of E_{corr} and the current density (i_{corr}) with the implantation dose. In all cases, ion implantation increases the E_{corr} and decreases the i_{corr} . The protection against corrosion is inversely proportional to the i_{corr} measured [32]. An increase in the i_{corr} value means degradation of the protective properties of the passive film [33–35]. In this case, the increase in E_{corr} is accompanied by a decrease in i_{corr} which confirms the improvement in the corrosion resistance of ion implanted AISI 304 SS. As occurred in the R_p experiments (Fig. 12), the modifications induced in the Ar-implanted specimen promoted the best protection conditions of AISI 304 SS, with the lowest i_{corr} . Nevertheless,

nitrogen and silicon implantation also improved the protective properties of the SS. An increase in E_{corr} was also observed by Veerabadran et al. [36] on N- implanted SS, although no previous results have been found in the literature relation with silicon and argon implantation on the E_{corr} or i_{corr} .

Fig. 14. E_{corr} and i_{corr} for non-implanted and N-, Ar- and Si-implanted AISI304 SS specimens.

Fig. 15 shows the anodic (β_a) and cathodic (β_c) slopes for AISI 304 SS with the implanted elements. Ion implantation increases β_a , hindering the anodic reaction, while smaller modifications were observed in β_c . Thus, N, Ar and Si implantation in these experimental conditions polarised the anodic reaction, increasing the protective properties and decreasing the corrosion process of the passive layer. The small variations found in the cathodic reaction show that no significant influence in this reaction may be attributed to the ion implantation process.

N-implantation is known to play an important role in modifying the anodic reaction, hindering the dissolution of the SS [33,35]. However, no influence of nitrogen on the cathodic reaction has been found in the literature, verifying the present results. Up to now, previous studies have not demonstrated that ion implantation of an inert gas like argon improves the corrosion resistance of SS, since no remarkable effect on corrosion behaviour has been found [37,38]. Takahashi and Iwaki [39] reported that argon implantation is not an effective method for inhibiting the anodic dissolution of iron. However, Bonora et al. [40] pointed out that the effect of argon implantation depends on the ion dose and the test solution. In the experimental conditions employed in this work, an impediment in anodic dissolution was found. On the other hand, the Si-implanted specimen presented the greatest impediment for the occurrence of the anodic reaction. The Si-rich layer on the outermost part of the passive film seems to cause a greater delay in anodic dissolution, increasing the protective properties.

Fig. 15. Tafel slopes (β_a and β_c) for non-implanted and N-, Ar- and Si- implanted AISI 304 SS specimens.

Fig. 16 shows E_{corr} and i_{corr} values for AISI 430 SS versus the implantation dose. It can be observed that ion implantation decreases the E_{corr} and increases the i_{corr} . Only the N-implanted specimen maintained similar values to the non-implanted specimen.

Fig. 17 shows the β_a and β_c slopes for AISI 430 SS with the implanted elements. An increase in the b_a value can be observed with N and Ar implantation, hindering the anodic reaction. In contrast, silicon implantation decreases b_a and favours the passive layer dissolution. The SiO_2 layer does not seem to be sufficiently stable. Once again, smaller modifications of b_c were obtained, and an increase can only be outlined with argon implantation. Therefore, despite the increase in i_{corr} , argon implantation hinders both the anodic and the cathodic reactions. On the other hand, silicon implantation enhances the corrosion process, favouring the anodic and the cathodic reactions. As a consequence, the constant B of the Stern-Geary equation:

$i_{\text{corr}} \propto \frac{1}{B}$, is modified and the relationship between i_{corr} and R_p changes, explaining the increase obtained in the R_p experiments. Finally, N-implanted specimen presents small modifications in the corrosion behaviour, which provided good protection for AISI 430 SS.

Fig. 16. E_{corr} and i_{corr} for non-implanted and N-, Ar- and Si-implanted AISI430 SS specimens.

Fig. 17. Tafel slopes (β_a and β_c) for non-implanted and N-, Ar- and Si-implanted AISI 430 SS specimens.

4. Conclusions

All the implanted elements can be found in the passive layers of AISI 304 and AISI 430 SSs. Nitrogen has no significant effect on the structure or composition of the passive layers and is not found to form chromium or iron nitrides. The main effect of argon implantation is to increase the Cr/Fe ratio of the passive layer, which is associated with an improvement in the corrosion resistance of implanted steels. The passive layer of silicon-implanted SSs has a very different structure, with an outer layer composed of SiO₂. Metallic oxides and/or hydroxides are found deeper in the passive layer of silicon-implanted steels.

Ion implantation increases the corrosion resistance of AISI 304 SS. The best protection conditions were obtained with argon implantation, with which the highest Cr/Fe ratio was obtained. Despite the Si-rich layer on the Si-implanted specimen, a favourable Cr/Fe ratio may promote a great increase in the protective properties of AISI 304 SS. However, different behaviour was obtained with AISI 430 SS, where despite the modification of the corrosion process, no clear improvement in the protective properties was observed.

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